

REDUCED OR NO-TILLAGE FARMING IS NOT THE HOLY GRAIL ANSWER

Reducing soil compaction does have clear positive effects. Rather than installing tillage bans, we might want to evolve more to less, well-timed and lighter machining on the land in general – and to a restoration of compacted soils in the process..

ADDING, RETURNING OR KEEPING ORGANIC MATERIAL

Organic carbon is like the mortar in the house of soil. It holds soil particles together and improves soil structure. The benefits of organic additions such as plant residues, compost, manure, wood chips and biochar cannot be denied.

DIFFERENT STROKES FOR DIFFERENT FOLKS, SOILS, FARMS AND FARMERS

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14974295](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974295)

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ADOPTION OF CLIMATE-SMART SOIL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND WATER REGULATION FUNCTIONS IN EUROPE

Covering the land with living plants works

Keeping the soil continuously covered with living plants stimulates soil life and carbon storage. Essential in developing a good soil structure.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

GOOD SOIL STRUCTURE ENSURES GOOD WATER INFILTRATION AND STORAGE.

This soil cover can be achieved in different ways: catch crops such as rapeseed or phacelia can offer solace in wintertime, grass can be sown under in corn fields and grass strips planted between rows of fruit trees.

All agricultural practices come with their own advantages and disadvantages. These plants will take up water as well, which can be a problem in regions that struggle with year-round drought.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT CLIMASOMA

The results of over 10,000 observations on soil management and crop system practices Year-round soil cover, organic matter additions and a reduction of traffic on agricultural land. No single management practice can be the one solution for all soils and climates: context is key!

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment.

SOIL MISSION: Conserve soil organic carbon stocks and improve soil structure

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
CLIMASOMA

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

EJP SOIL has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme: Grant
agreement No 862695

